

Supplemental data

Accelerated early childhood growth associates with the development of earlier adrenarche and puberty

Jani Liimatta^{1,2,3}, Jarmo Jääskeläinen^{1,4}, Aino Mäntyselkä^{1,4}, Merja R. Häkkinen^{5,6}, Seppo Auriola⁵,
Raimo Voutilainen^{1,4}, Christa E. Flück^{2,3}, Timo A. Lakka^{7,8,9}

¹ Kuopio Pediatric Research Unit (KuPRU), University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland

² Department of BioMedical Research (DBMR), University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland

³ Pediatric Endocrinology, Diabetology, and Metabolism, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, Bern, Switzerland

⁴ Department of Pediatrics, Kuopio University Hospital, Kuopio, Finland

⁵ School of Pharmacy, University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland

⁶ Department of Health Security, Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Kuopio, Finland

⁷ Institute of Biomedicine, School of Medicine, University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland

⁸ Department of Clinical Physiology and Nuclear Medicine, Kuopio University Hospital, Kuopio, Finland

⁹ Foundation for Research in Health Exercise and Nutrition, Kuopio Research Institute of Exercise Medicine, Kuopio, Finland

Supplemental Table 1. Anthropometric data separately in girls and boys. Data is presented for all girls or boys, and for the groups clustered by their birth size (BS) and postnatal growth (PG; 0-5 years).

	Groups based on the Kmeans clustering analyses					p ^a
	All	AI: Average BS and Increased PG	SI: Small BS and Increased PG	AA: Average BS and Average PG	SA: Small BS and Average PG	
Girls						
Anthropometrics (0-5 yrs)						
Birth weight SDS	-0.09 (0.95)	0.29 (0.81)	-0.73 (0.67)	0.50 (0.66)	-0.85 (0.84)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 0.5 yrs	-0.07 (1.07)	0.91 (0.84)	-0.29 (0.82)	0.09 (0.92)	-1.14 (0.59)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 2 yrs	-0.08 (1.09)	1.09 (0.90)	0.01 (0.84)	-0.15 (0.64)	-1.39 (0.70)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 5 yrs	0.01 (1.11)	1.21 (0.85)	0.15 (0.63)	-0.02 (0.70)	-1.33 (0.71)	< 0.001
Δweight SDS (0-5 yrs)	0.09 (1.21)	0.92 (1.17)	0.84 (0.92)	-0.52 (0.89)	-0.48 (1.06)	< 0.001
Birth length SDS	-0.21 (0.95)	0.24 (0.78)	-1.10 (0.64)	0.44 (0.58)	-0.85 (0.71)	< 0.001
Length SDS at age 0.5 yrs	-0.35 (1.09)	0.64 (0.85)	-0.70 (0.91)	-0.03 (0.70)	-1.52 (0.76)	< 0.001
Height SDS at age 2 yrs	-0.22 (0.93)	0.81 (0.65)	-0.26 (0.61)	-0.22 (0.70)	-1.32 (0.58)	< 0.001
Height SDS at age 5 yrs	-0.05 (0.93)	1.14 (0.66)	0.07 (0.67)	-0.17 (0.62)	-1.18 (0.59)	< 0.001
Δlength/Height SDS (0-5 yrs)	0.15 (1.18)	0.89 (0.92)	1.15 (0.98)	-0.62 (0.89)	-0.33 (0.82)	< 0.001
At baseline examination						
Weight SDS	-0.05 (1.05)	0.89 (0.86)	0.19 (0.85)	-0.10 (0.72)	-1.15 (0.85)	< 0.001
Height SDS	0.11 (0.97)	1.13 (0.75)	0.27 (0.74)	0.05 (0.63)	-0.97 (0.62)	< 0.001
BMI SDS	-0.16 (1.13)	0.52 (1.06)	0.02 (1.17)	-0.21 (0.92)	-0.92 (1.00)	< 0.001
Waist-to-height percentage	44.1 (4.2)	45.8 (5.1)	44.4 (4.5)	43.6 (3.3)	42.7 (3.0)	0.006
Fat percentage ^b	22.6 (8.0)	27.3 (8.3)	24.0 (8.9)	21.7 (6.6)	17.8 (5.6)	< 0.001
Growth velocity, cm/yr ^c	6.63 (0.63)	6.68 (0.73)	6.76 (0.59)	6.69 (0.57)	6.36 (0.59)	0.024
At follow-up examination						
Weight SDS	-0.08 (1.00)	0.69 (0.82)	0.18 (0.86)	-0.13 (0.72)	-1.11 (0.84)	< 0.001
Height SDS	0.05 (0.92)	0.96 (0.80)	0.21 (0.73)	-0.05 (0.63)	-0.92 (0.62)	< 0.001
BMI SDS	-0.16 (1.04)	0.37 (0.97)	0.04 (1.08)	-0.19 (0.85)	-0.91 (0.99)	< 0.001
Waist-to-height percentage	43.0 (4.4)	44.2 (5.3)	43.7 (5.3)	42.6 (3.5)	41.3 (3.4)	0.032
Fat percentage ^b	30.3 (7.8)	34.1 (7.8)	29.2 (8.3)	30.6 (6.9)	27.9 (8.7)	< 0.001

Growth velocity, cm/yr ^d	5.55 (0.66)	5.72 (0.75)	5.66 (0.63)	5.53 (0.66)	5.31 (0.52)	0.039
Boys						
Anthropometrics (0-5 yrs)						
Birth weight SDS	-0.12 (0.97)	0.35 (0.81)	-0.88 (0.69)	0.46 (0.73)	-0.83 (0.73)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 0.5 yrs	-0.01 (0.99)	1.18 (0.76)	-0.20 (0.71)	-0.12 (0.75)	-0.86 (0.64)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 2 yrs	-0.07 (1.08)	1.21 (0.67)	0.04 (0.71)	-0.19 (0.65)	-1.38 (0.51)	< 0.001
Weight SDS at age 5 yrs	-0.02 (1.10)	1.25 (0.74)	0.26 (0.71)	-0.15 (0.59)	-1.22 (0.88)	< 0.001
Δweight SDS (0-5 yrs)	0.13 (1.23)	0.88 (1.03)	1.13 (1.01)	-0.61 (0.89)	-0.39 (0.99)	< 0.001
Birth length SDS	-0.20 (0.98)	0.34 (0.81)	-0.98 (0.58)	0.39 (0.61)	-0.96 (0.92)	< 0.001
Length SDS at age 0.5 yrs	-0.20 (1.05)	1.12 (0.61)	-0.70 (0.56)	-0.06 (0.76)	-1.22 (0.67)	< 0.001
Height SDS at age 2 yrs	-0.15 (0.99)	1.04 (0.70)	-0.39 (0.58)	-0.16 (0.69)	-1.20 (0.50)	< 0.001
Height SDS at age 5 yrs	0.03 (1.03)	1.21 (0.70)	-0.04 (0.53)	0.03 (0.58)	-1.20 (0.79)	< 0.001
Δlength/Height SDS (0-5 yrs)	0.21 (1.10)	0.88 (1.00)	0.87 (0.82)	-0.35 (0.83)	-0.24 (1.10)	< 0.001
At baseline examination						
Weight SDS	-0.14 (1.02)	0.91 (0.73)	0.25 (0.79)	-0.15 (0.78)	-1.07 (0.82)	< 0.001
Height SDS	0.21 (1.01)	1.34 (0.80)	0.17 (0.60)	0.18 (0.62)	-0.92 (0.72)	< 0.001
BMI SDS	-0.19 (1.10)	0.42 (0.94)	0.14 (1.16)	-0.42 (1.00)	-0.83 (0.93)	< 0.001
Waist-to-height percentage	44.0 (3.6)	44.8 (3.9)	45.1 (4.3)	43.2 (3.1)	43.4 (3.1)	0.015
Fat percentage ^b	22.2 (10.1)	26.3 (10.2)	25.2 (10.4)	19.7 (9.2)	18.2 (8.6)	< 0.001
Growth velocity, cm/yr ^c	6.81 (0.98)	7.06 (0.60)	6.82 (0.60)	6.76 (0.66)	6.58 (1.73)	0.149
At follow-up examination						
Weight SDS	-0.01 (1.03)	0.83 (0.78)	0.25 (0.82)	-0.21 (0.85)	-0.92 (0.89)	< 0.001
Height SDS	0.18 (1.01)	1.27 (0.84)	0.17 (0.61)	0.10 (0.71)	-0.93 (0.68)	< 0.001
BMI SDS	-0.13 (1.09)	0.42 (0.95)	0.17 (1.09)	-0.38 (1.00)	-0.67 (1.01)	< 0.001
Waist-to-height percentage	44.0 (4.3)	45.2 (4.5)	45.2 (5.0)	42.9 (3.2)	43.4 (4.4)	0.012
Fat percentage ^b	17.3 (9.4)	20.0 (11.2)	20.5 (10.2)	14.3 (7.5)	14.3 (5.3)	< 0.001
Growth velocity, cm/yr ^d	5.37 (0.64)	5.67 (0.64)	5.47 (0.64)	5.27 (0.64)	5.10 (0.48)	< 0.001

Values are expressed as means (standard deviation). P-values of < 0.05 indicating statistically significant differences between groups are bolded.

Notes: ^a, p-values for overall differences between groups from analysis of variance for continuous variables and from Pearson's Chi-Square test for categorical variables; ^b, excluding head and measured by dual x-ray absorptiometry; ^c, calculated using age and height values at age 5 yrs and at baseline examination (years); ^d, calculated using age and height values at baseline (6-9 yrs) and at follow-up examination (9-11 yrs).

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; BS, birth size; PG, postnatal growth; SDS, standard deviation score; Δ, change between two time points.

Supplemental Table 2. Data of sexual development at age 6-9 and 9-11 years in all girls and boys, and in the groups clustered by birth size (BS) and postnatal growth (PG; 0-5 years).

	Groups based on the Kmeans clustering analyses					p ^a
	All	AI: Average BS and Increased PG	SI: Small BS and Increased PG	AA: Average BS and Average PG	SA: Small BS and Average PG	
Girls						
At baseline examination						
Clinical adrenarche, yes % ^b	28	32	24	25	32	0.768
Biochemical adrenarche, yes % ^c	19	29	29	8	19	0.021
Clinical or biochemical adrenarche, yes %	38	43	46	27	44	0.157
Pubarche, yes % ^d	1	3	0	0	3	0.430
Clinical puberty, yes % ^e	5	5	14	3	0	0.051
At follow-up examination						
Clinical adrenarche, yes % ^b	71	81	80	67	58	0.099
Biochemical adrenarche, yes % ^c	29	49	42	15	30	0.012
Clinical or biochemical adrenarche, yes %	73	81	88	67	62	0.034
Pubarche, yes % ^d	15	22	17	13	9	0.521
Clinical puberty, yes % ^e	33	51	44	28	12	0.002
Biochemical puberty, yes % ^f	19	39	13	16	7	0.003
Clinical or biochemical puberty, yes %	36	57	44	31	12	< 0.001
Boys						
At baseline examination						
Clinical adrenarche, yes % ^b	9	7	15	9	3	0.262
Biochemical adrenarche, yes % ^c	17	11	12	21	20	0.446
Clinical or biochemical adrenarche, yes %	25	19	25	28	24	0.713
Pubarche, yes % ^d	0	0	0	0	0	> 0.999
Clinical puberty, yes % ^e	2	5	0	3	0	0.353
At follow-up examination						
Clinical adrenarche, yes % ^b	56	66	56	56	47	0.457
Biochemical adrenarche, yes % ^c	34	33	29	37	35	0.863

Clinical or biochemical adrenarche, yes %	67	69	62	71	62	0.694
Pubarche, yes % ^d	3	0	8	3	0	0.129
Clinical puberty, yes % ^e	14	21	14	10	11	0.460
Biochemical puberty, yes % ^f	13	18	17	9	11	0.597
Clinical or biochemical puberty, yes %	21	31	25	14	19	0.188

Values are expressed as proportion in percentage. P-values of < 0.05 indicating statistically significant differences between groups are bolded.

Notes: ^a, p-values for overall differences between groups from Pearson's Chi-Square test; ^b, at least one clinical sign of adrenarche (adult-type body odor, oily skin, comedones/acne, axillary or pubic hair); ^c, serum dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS) concentration $\geq 1 \mu\text{mol/l}$; ^d, Tanner P ≥ 2 ; ^e, Tanner B ≥ 2 in girls and Tanner G ≥ 2 together with testicular volume $\geq 4 \text{ ml}$ in boys; ^f, serum luteinizing hormone concentration $\geq 0.3 \text{ U/l}$.

Abbreviations: BS, birth size; PG, postnatal growth.

Supplemental Table 3. Biochemical data for all girls and boys, and for the groups clustered by birth size (BS) and postnatal growth (PG) trajectory.

	Groups based on the Kmeans clustering analyses					p ^a
	All	AI: Average BS and increased PG	SI: Small BS and increased PG	AA: Average BS and average PG	SA: Small BS and average PG	
Girls						
At baseline examination (6-9 yrs)						
DHEA, nmol/l	1.96 (1.03-3.18)	2.58 (1.17-4.08)	2.97 (2.18-4.85)	1.48 (0.75-2.06)	1.79 (1.00-3.56)	< 0.001
DHEAS, μmol/l	1.13 (0.01-2.69)	0.70 (0.40-1.09)	0.72 (0.51-1.05)	0.50 (0.31-0.64)	0.48 (0.28-0.85)	0.001
A4, nmol/l	0.79 (0.49-1.19)	0.86 (0.55-1.26)	0.96 (0.61-1.36)	0.74 (0.43-1.04)	0.74 (0.45-1.16)	0.047
T, pmol/l	132 (92-194)	149 (95-247)	149 (117-212)	123 (87-161)	120 (72-203)	0.035
At follow-up examination (9-11 yrs)						
DHEA, nmol/l	3.81 (2.33-5.82)	4.70 (2.92-7.04)	4.60 (3.51-6.94)	2.81 (1.69-4.69)	3.95 (2.07-6.80)	0.005
DHEAS, μmol/l	0.69 (0.41-1.04)	0.84 (0.45-1.31)	0.92 (0.60-1.25)	0.62 (0.36-0.86)	0.59 (0.22-1.16)	0.003
A4, nmol/l	1.34 (0.91-1.97)	1.70 (0.96-2.60)	1.41 (1.06-2.12)	1.16 (0.84-1.66)	1.31 (0.64-1.89)	0.029
T, pmol/l	230 (156-343)	288 (198-487)	246 (168-356)	204 (138-304)	199 (124-310)	0.014
Boys						
At baseline examination (6-9 yrs)						
DHEA, nmol/l	1.30 (0.74-2.29)	1.05 (0.67-1.70)	1.68 (0.73-3.31)	1.31 (0.70-2.11)	1.65 (0.83-2.53)	0.337
DHEAS, μmol/l	0.60 (0.34-0.85)	0.63 (0.41-0.87)	0.63 (0.33-0.81)	0.56 (0.33-0.96)	0.55 (0.36-0.89)	0.928
A4, nmol/l	0.66 (0.48-0.96)	0.61 (0.50-0.93)	0.71 (0.47-0.91)	0.71 (0.46-0.99)	0.61 (0.48-1.01)	0.939
T, pmol/l	115 (77-164)	98 (69-147)	140 (84-169)	116 (75-164)	110 (81-162)	0.345
At follow-up examination (9-11 yrs)						
DHEA, nmol/l	3.01 (1.96-4.50)	2.55 (1.67-3.72)	3.22 (2.08-4.47)	3.32 (2.22-4.88)	3.08 (1.52-3.90)	0.419
DHEAS, μmol/l	0.74 (0.42-1.15)	0.71 (0.36-1.13)	0.69 (0.43-1.25)	0.77 (0.41-1.21)	0.74 (0.44-1.11)	0.633
A4, nmol/l	1.09 (0.42-1.15)	0.99 (0.72-1.37)	1.12 (0.92-1.40)	1.26 (0.90-1.63)	1.08 (0.71-1.51)	0.471
T, pmol/l	187 (134-257)	182 (132-222)	198 (142-309)	188 (131-291)	184 (129-241)	0.183

Values are expressed as medians (25th-75th percentile range). P-values of < 0.05 indicating statistically significant differences between groups are bolded.

Notes: ^a, p-values for overall differences between groups from analysis of variance.

Abbreviations: A4, androstenedione; BS, birth size; DHEA, dehydroepiandrosterone; DHEAS, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate; PG, postnatal growth; T, testosterone.

Supplemental Table 4. Logistic regression models with body length/height measures (0-5 years) as predictors of having clinical or biochemical signs of adrenarche or puberty in mid-childhood or in early adolescence.

	Girls (n = 176)			Boys (n = 192)		
	OR	95% CI	p	OR	95% CI	p
Any clinical sign of androgen action at age 6-9 years ^a						
Birth length SDS	1.12	0.67-1.88	0.673	0.60	0.26-1.39	0.231
ΔLength SDS (0-0.5 yrs)	1.46	0.88-2.41	0.144	0.91	0.43-1.93	0.810
ΔHeight SDS (0.5-2 yrs)	1.59	0.90-2.81	0.108	1.17	0.38-3.58	0.784
ΔHeight SDS (2-5 yrs)	1.55	0.79-3.04	0.206	4.54	1.27-16.2	0.020
Serum DHEAS ≥ 1 μmol/l at age 6-9 years ^a						
Birth length SDS	0.76	0.44-1.34	0.347	1.02	0.61-1.70	0.952
ΔLength SDS (0-0.5 yrs)	1.34	0.77-2.33	0.297	1.17	0.71-1.95	0.537
ΔHeight SDS (0.5-2 yrs)	2.23	1.18-4.21	0.014	1.59	0.76-3.32	0.215
ΔHeight SDS (2-5 yrs)	1.49	0.71-3.15	0.293	1.48	0.69-3.18	0.315
Pubarche (Tanner P ≥ 2) at age 9-11 years ^b						
Birth length SDS	1.55	0.80-2.98	0.191	1.18	0.32-4.31	0.804
ΔLength SDS (0-0.5 yrs)	1.81	0.97-3.37	0.061	0.72	0.21-2.48	0.598
ΔHeight SDS (0.5-2 yrs)	2.71	1.33-5.50	0.006	0.87	0.13-6.00	0.869
ΔHeight SDS (2-5 yrs)	2.70	1.15-6.29	0.022	1.20	0.19-7.58	0.849
Pubertal onset at age 9-11 years ^b						
Birth length SDS	1.75	0.98-3.12	0.060	1.11	0.61-2.04	0.729
ΔLength SDS (0-0.5 yrs)	1.89	1.10-3.26	0.022	1.00	0.55-1.80	0.987
ΔHeight SDS (0.5-2 yrs)	2.95	1.52-5.70	0.001	1.06	0.44-2.58	0.891
ΔHeight SDS (2-5 yrs)	2.17	1.03-4.55	0.040	1.93	0.74-5.00	0.177
Serum LH ≥ 0.3 U/l at age 9-11 years ^b						
Birth length SDS	1.84	0.96-3.55	0.068	0.62	0.32-1.21	0.164
ΔLength SDS (0-0.5 yrs)	2.54	1.37-4.70	0.003	0.87	0.45-1.67	0.676
ΔHeight SDS (0.5-2 yrs)	2.42	1.19-4.90	0.014	0.62	0.24-1.64	0.338
ΔHeight SDS (2-5 yrs)	1.54	0.70-3.38	0.287	1.19	0.43-3.28	0.732

P-values of < 0.05 indicating statistically significant differences between groups are bolded. Pubertal onset was defined as Tanner B ≥ 2 for girls and Tanner G ≥ 2 together with testicular volume ≥ 4 ml in boys.

Notes: ^a, adjusted with fat percentage (excluding head and measured by dual x-ray absorptiometry) at age 6-9 years; ^b, adjusted with fat percentage (excluding head and measured by dual x-ray absorptiometry) at age 9-11 years.

Abbreviations: OR, odds ratio; SDS, standard deviation score; Δ, change between two time points.

Supplemental Figure 1a. An example of a Python script on how Kmeans clustering analysis was performed in this study.

```
#Import appropriate modules
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import pyreadstat
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import os
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score
```

```
os.chdir('X:\\dirpath')
cwd = os.getcwd()
df = pd.read_spss(cwd + '\\filename.sav')
df
```

```
#new df with desired columns and without NaN-values
df1 = df[['list of columns']].dropna().round(2)
```

```
#Example of growth variable normalization to follow a parametric distribution in a range of -1 to +1:
```

```
#Mean and standard deviation for growth variables
VARIABLE_X_mean = df1['X'].mean()
VARIABLE_X_std = df1['X'].std()

# standardized value = (value - mean) / std
df1['X_normalized'] = (df1['X'] - VARIABLE_X_mean) / VARIABLE_X_std
```

```
#check if normalized values are as they should be (means = close to zero; range from -1 to +1 (ie standard deviation = 1))
```

```
df_normalized = df1[['list of normalized columns']]
print('means')
print(df_normalized.mean().round(2))
print('standard deviations')
print(df_normalized.std().round(2))
```

```
#Making an array and checking the shape
array = df_normalized.to_numpy(copy=True).astype(np.float64)
array.shape
```

```
#Clustering analyses
```

```
#Silhouette scores for detecting the most appropriate no of clusters (in range of 2 to 8)
```

```
plt.figure()
res = []
for itrials in range(2,9):
    clusterer = KMeans(n_clusters=itrials, random_state=10)
    cluster_labels = clusterer.fit_predict(array)
    score=silhouette_score(array,cluster_labels)
    res.append(score)

plt.xlabel('Number of clusters', fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel('Silhouette score', fontsize=14)
plt.tick_params(axis='x', labelsz=14)
plt.tick_params(axis='y', labelsz=14)
plt.plot(np.arange(len(res))+2, res, '-o')
plt.savefig('silhuettescores.tif', format='tif', dpi=300)
plt.show()
```

```
#Inertia values (i.e. "Elbow" -method) for detecting the most appropriate no of clusters (in range of 2 to 8)
```

```
wss = []
for i in range(2,9):
    kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters = i, init = 'k-means++')
    kmeans.fit(array)
    wss.append(kmeans.inertia_)

frame = pd.DataFrame({'Cluster':range(2,9), 'WSS':wss})
plt.figure()
plt.plot(frame['Cluster'], frame['WSS'], marker='o')
plt.xlabel('Number of clusters', fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel('Inertia value', fontsize=14)
plt.tick_params(axis='x', labelsz=14)
plt.tick_params(axis='y', labelsz=12)
plt.savefig('inertia.tif', format='tif', dpi=300)
plt.show()
```

Supplemental Figure 1b. An example of a Python script on how Kmeans clustering analysis was performed in this study (continued from Supplemental Figure 1a).

```
#Predicting individuals to cluster groups
clusterer = KMeans(n_clusters='no of clusters', random_state=10)
cluster_labels = clusterer.fit_predict(array)
df1['clusters'] = cluster_labels.astype('str')

#replace cluster values if needed
df1["clusters"].replace({"old value1": "new value1", "old value2": "new value2", ...}, inplace=True)

#grouping
clustered = df1.groupby('clusters')
cluster1 = clustered.get_group('1')
cluster2 = clustered.get_group('2')
...

print('A total of X individuals are clustered as follows: ')
print(clustered.size())

#An example on how the growth images were produced for visual analyses
#df had been restructured to long format

fig, ax = plt.subplots()
sns.lineplot(data=df_long_format, x='time', y='weight', hue='clusters', style='clusters', err_style='band', palette='icefire')
ax.set_ylim([-2, 2])
ax.set_xticks((1, 2, 3, 4))
ax.set_xticklabels(('Birth', '6 mo', '2 y', '5 y'))
ax.tick_params(axis='x', labelsz=16)
ax.tick_params(axis='y', labelsz=14)
ax.set_xlabel('Age', fontsize=18)
ax.set_ylabel('Weight SDS', fontsize=18)
plt.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(1, 1), loc='upper left').set_title('Clusters')
handles, labels = ax.get_legend_handles_labels()
legend = ax.legend(handles, labels, ncol=2, frameon=True, fontsize=16, loc='upper left', bbox_to_anchor=(1, 1)).set_title('Clusters')
#plt.savefig('clustersweight.jpg', dpi = 300, bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
```

Supplemental Figure 2. Silhouette scores (panel A) and inertia values (panel B) from unsupervised Kmeans clustering analyses to detect optimal number of clusters. Data used for this clustering analysis included standardized weight and length/height values at birth and at age 0.5, 2, and 5 years.

A)

B)

Supplemental Figure 3. Weight (left panels) and length/height (right panels) SDS from birth to age 5 years in all children predicted to clusters in range of 2-5 clusters (panels A-D). Cluster predictions were based on unsupervised Kmeans clustering analysis.

Supplemental Figure 4. Change (Δ) in weight (left panels) and length/height (right panels) SDS from birth to age 5 years in all children predicted to clusters in range of 2-5 clusters (panels A-D). Cluster predictions were based on unsupervised Kmeans clustering analysis.

